

BULLYING IN THE SCHOOL ENVIRONMENT: A CASE STUDY FROM ALBANIA**Lorenc Barjami¹****Juventina Ngjela²****Irena Xhaferi³****Laura Longhi⁴****Elton Kazanxhi⁵****Ledion Musaj⁶****Edvaldo Begotaraj⁷**¹ *Sapienza University of Rome*, Italy² *Albanian University, Tirana, Albania*³ *Sapienza University of Rome, Italy*⁴ *Wisdom University, Tirana, Albania*⁵ *University of Tirana, Albania*⁶ *Wisdom University, Tirana, Albania*⁷ *Sapienza University of Rome***Abstract**

This study aims to shed light on female and male students' attitudes in ninth grade towards bullying cases in the school environment. From the methodology point of view, this is quantitative research. For the purposes of the study, it was employed a questionnaire to evaluate female and male students' attitudes toward bullying. The Statistical Package for Social Sciences was implemented for the data analysis. ANOVA analysis showed that there is no statistically significant difference between female and male students' attitudes in ninth grade towards bullying cases in the school environment.

Keywords: school; bullying; female and male student attitudes; gender differences

1. Introduction

Bullying in school is one of the most significant issues worldwide and one of the most common antisocial behaviors among children and adolescents. This phenomenon affects all students, the person who bullies, those who are victims, and those who are witnesses in a bullying situation. According to Olweus "Bullying is an intentional and repeated act which happens through physical, verbal, and relational forms in situations where a power differential is present." Alison (2016) mentioned that bullying is a global problem that affects the emotional, social, and physical well-being of school-age children worldwide. Shafqat (2015, 45) argued that bullying in schools affects school students in many parts of their lives such as; psychologically, educationally, and professionally (Omoteso, 2010) stressed that Bullying is a common increasing problem in every society and school whereas (Kartal & Asude, 2009) stated that Bullying occurs at any time and it has negative impacts mostly on students' academic, emotional, and social development during the school period. The World Health Organization (2002) recognizes bullying behavior as the intentional use of physical and psychological force or power, threatened or actual, against oneself, another person, or against a group or community that either results in or has a high likelihood of resulting in injury, death, psychological harm, maldevelopment, or deprivation. School bullying and peer victimization are major social problems affecting children and adolescents in all parts of the world. The serious consequences of bullying and peer victimization have generated a considerable amount of attention from the media and the public, as well as educators, school officials, researchers, practitioners, and lawmakers in recent years (Phillips, 2007). Bosworth, Espelage, and

Simon (1999) examined bullying behavior among 558 sixth-to-eighth-grade students at a large middle school located in a major Midwestern metropolis. They reported that 81% of the students reported being victimized by their peers, and 7.7% reported frequently bullying someone in school. Glew, Fan, Katon, Rivara & Kernic's (2005) investigated the prevalence of bullying among elementary schools in an urban, West Coast public school district, reporting that 22% of children surveyed were involved in bullying, as victim, bully, or both. In sum, the prevalence of bullying is high for children of all educational levels. Many studies report that boys in general are more likely to engage in bullying than girls (Espelage, Bosworth, & Simon, 2000; Nansel et al., 2001; Rigby, 1997; Ross, 1996; Seals & Young, 2003; Varjas et al., 2009). Past findings also indicated that boys are commonly victims and perpetrators of direct forms of bullying, while girls experience indirect bullying (e.g., social rejection, and relational aggression) (Olweus, 1993; Varjas et al., 2009).

Narayanan and Betts (2014) investigated bullying in Indian adolescents aged between 14 and 20 years old. It was found that male adolescents engaged in bullying behaviors and experienced victimization more frequently than female adolescents. (Mynard & Joseph 1997, and Jordan & Austin 2012) stressed that students who have been bullied are likely to suffer from school and social competence and find it difficult to negotiate with parents and teachers. Espelage and Holt (2001) investigated the prevalence rates of bullying by gender and grade level in an American sample of children and early adolescents. They found no significant difference between grade levels, nevertheless, there were significant differences by gender. Males had a higher level of

bullying and victimization than females. Relevant research has shown a trend toward gender differences in preferred forms of aggression, with boys being generally more aggressive than girls and girls being predominantly more indirectly aggressive than boys, especially during adolescence (Bjorkqvist, Lagerspetz & Kaukiainen, 1992; Crick & Grotpeter, 1995; Salmivalli & Kaukiainen, 2004; Smith et al., 2002; Whitney & Smith, 1993). Researchers found that boys were more frequently designated, through self and peer evaluations, as bullies than were girls and that boys more often participated in bullying as reinforcers and assistants, whereas girls were outsiders and defenders (Salmivalli, Lagerspetz, Bjorkqvist, Osterman & Kaukiainen, 1996). Seals and Young (2003) conducted an American sample of seventh and eighth graders, and they found that males had higher scores on the bullying scale than females, and that seventh graders scored higher on this scale than eighth. A study by Scheithauer, Hayer, Peretman & Jugert (2006) studied differences in bullying among a sample of German students from 5th to 10th grades. Based on the findings of the study was found that males had a higher tendency to bully other students than females and the males who were classified as bully-victims were more than females. According to some research, boys are more prone to be both bullies and victims of bullying since girls are more likely to engage in situations of indirect bullying. In a recent study using a representative sample of 1,500 Spanish students in compulsory secondary school during the 2007-2008 academic years, it was revealed that boys have been involved in all forms of bullying cases compared to girls.

2. Methodology

2.1. Objective

This study aims to answer the following research questions:

- 1- Is there any difference between female and male students with respect to bullying cases in the school environment?
- 2- Is there any difference between female and male students with regard to seeking psychological help from the school psychologist due to bullying experiences?
- 3- Is there any difference between female and male students with respect to being a protagonist in

bullying someone in the school environment?

2.2. Participants

The population of this study is made up of female and male students in ninth grade belonging to "Meleq Gosnishti" a 9-year elementary school in Perme. 24 Students were interviewed through the convenience sampling method.

2.3. Instrument

The study employed a questionnaire to assess female and male students' attitudes toward bullying in the school environment. The questionnaire comprises 10 questions that aim to evaluate the differences between female and male students with respect to bullying cases in the school environment.

2.4. Procedure

Students, teachers, school directors, and parents were initially informed about the study and its purpose. The parental consent form was given to the parents to receive permission to allow their children to participate in the study because all the students were under eighteen; in addition, before distributing the questionnaire to the students, the written informed consent of the director of the school was obtained. After receiving the permission, the questionnaire was piloted in a smaller group before applying it to the targeted sample. The questionnaire was administered in the classrooms without the presence of their teachers. Before the application of the questionnaire, the students were informed about the confidentiality issue and the purpose of the questionnaire. In addition, the participants were informed about the basic concepts included in the questionnaire such as physical violence, verbal violence, physical bullying, sexual bullying, etc. At the end of the questionnaire, all students were thanked for their voluntary participation.

2.5. Data analysis

The results were analyzed with the SPSS version 21, and the findings of the study might help other researchers to conduct other similar studies to shed more light on this issue.

3. Results

3.1. Data analysis through ANOVA.

In this part of the study, has been used ONE WAY ANOVA is one of the most effective methods for analyzing and interpreting the differences between the averages of variables.

Table 1.
ANOVA for the correspondence between female and male students with respect to bullying cases in the school environment.

ANOVA					
School bullying cases between female and male students from "Meleq Gosnishti" 9- year elementary school					
	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	.375	1	.375	.040	.844
Within Groups	208.250	22	9.466		
Total	208.625	23			

Table 1 shows that there is no statistically significant difference between female and male students with respect to bullying cases in the school environment, $F(1, 22) = 0.040$, $P = 0.844 > 0.05$, ($P > \alpha$).

Figure 1 shows the correspondence of the mean level of bullying cases in the school environment between female and male students from “Meleq Gosnishti “ 9 - a year elementary school

Figure 1

Figure 1 indicated that the mean level of female students with regard to bullying cases in the school environments $M = 17$ whereas the mean level of male students concerning bullying cases is $M = 17.25$ which means that female students have been less exposed to bullying cases in the school environment than male students.

Table 2 ANOVA for the correspondence between female and male students with regard to seeking psychological help from the school psychologist because of bullying experiences.

Table 2.

If you have experienced bullying in the classroom have you ever talked with the school psychologist about it					
	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	.000	1	.000		
Within Groups	3.333	22	.152	.000	1.000
Total	3.333	23			

Table 2 indicates that there is no statistically significant difference between female and male students with respect to seeking psychological help from the school psychologist because of bullying experiences, $F(1, 22) = 0.00$, $P = 1 > 0.05$, ($P > \alpha$).

Figure 2 Indicates that the mean level of female students with respect to seeking psychological help from the school psychologist because of bullying experiences is M

$= 1.83$ while the mean level of male students as far as concerned talking to the school psychologist because of bullying experiences is $M = 1.83$. As can be seen

from the figure there is no difference in the mean level between female and male students from “Meleq Gosnishti” 9-year elementary school with regard to seeking psychological help from the school psychologist because of bullying experiences. Taking these findings into consideration can be concluded that although both female and male students in ninth grade coming from “Meleq Gosnishti” 9-year elementary school have been bullied in the school environment, they have never sought psychological help from the school psychologist.

Figure 2

Table 3 ANOVA for the correspondence between female and male students with regard to being a protagonist in bullying someone in the school environment

Table 3.

Have you ever been a protagonist bullying someone in your school environment					
	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	.042	1	.042	.234	.633
Within Groups	3.917	22	.178		
Total	3.958	23			

Table 3 shows that there is no statistically significant difference between female and male students with regard to being a protagonist in bullying someone in the school environment, $F(1, 22) = 0.234$, $P = 0.633 > 0.05$, ($P > \alpha$).

Figure 3 indicates the correspondence of the mean level of female students and male students with regard to being a protagonist in bullying someone in the school environment

Fig. 3 Gender

Figure 3. This shows that the mean level of female students with respect to being a protagonist in bullying someone in the school environment is $M = 1.83$ whereas the mean level of male students with regard to being a protagonist in bullying someone in the school environment is $M = 1.75$. This is a pretty unexpected finding showing that female students have been more involved in being a protagonist in bullying someone in the school environment than male students. I want to emphasize that these findings should not be generalized and are only valid for these targeted categories mentioned above.

Discussions

For the purpose of this study was to shed light on female and male students' attitudes in ninth grade towards bullying cases in the school environment. The population of this study is made up of females and males in ninth grade belonging to a 9-year elementary school in Permet city. 24 students were interviewed through the convenience sampling method

This study is intended to find some scientific responses to the research questions below:

- 1- Is there any difference between female and male students with respect to bullying cases in the school environment?

Regarding the first question was used ANOVA. Table 1 shows that there is no statistically significant difference between female and male students with respect to bullying cases in the school environment, $F(1, 22) = 0.040$, $P = 0.844 > 0.05$, ($P > \alpha$). Figure 1 indicated that the mean level of female students with regard to bullying cases is $M = 17$ whereas the mean level of male students with regard to bullying cases is $M = 17.25$ which means that female students have been less exposed to bullying cases in the school environment than male students.

2- Is there any difference between female and male students with respect to seeking psychological help from the school psychologist because of bullying experiences?

For the second question was used ANOVA. Table 2 indicated that there is no statistically significant difference between female and male students with respect to seeking psychological help from the school psychologist because of bullying experiences, $F(1, 22) = 0.00$, $P = 1 > 0.05$, ($P > \alpha$). Figure 2. Showed that the mean level of female students with respect to seeking psychological help from the school psychologist because of bullying experiences is $M = 1.83$ while the mean level of male students as far as concerned talking to the school psychologist because of bullying experiences is $M = 1.83$. As can be seen from Figure 2. there is no difference in the mean level between female and male students from "Meleq Gosnishti" 9-year elementary school with regard to seeking psychological help from the school psychologist because of bullying experiences. Based on these findings can be concluded that although both female and male students in ninth grade coming from "Meleq Gosnishti" 9-year elementary school have been bullied in the school environment, they have never sought psychological help from the school psychologist.

3- Is there any difference between female and male students with regard to being a protagonist in bullying someone in the school environment?

Regarding the third question was used ANOVA. Table 3 showed that there is no statistically significant difference between female and male students with regard to being a protagonist in bullying someone in the school environment, $F(1, 22) = 0.234$, $P = 0.633 > 0.05$, ($P > \alpha$). Figure 3 Indicated that the mean level of female students with respect to being a protagonist in bullying someone in the school environment is M

$= 1.83$ whereas the mean level of male students with regard to being a protagonist in bullying someone in the school environment is $M = 1.75$. This means that female students have been more involved in being a protagonist in bullying someone in the school environment than male students.

BACK MATTER

Acknowledgments

The authors would like to thank different collaborators of "Meleq Gosnishti" 9-year Elementary School" and Wisdom University for their support and assistance in different ways during the research.

Funding

This study is financed by Wisdom University, Tirana, Albania.

Conflict of interest

There are no conflicts of interest.

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References

- Al-Raqad H. Khaled, Al-Bourini E. Saeed, Al Talahin F. Mohammad, Aranki R. G. Elias. (2017). The impact of school bullying on students' academic achievement from teachers point of view. *International Education Studies*, 10(6), doi.org/10.5539/ies.v10n6p44.
- Athanasiades, C., & Deliyanni-Kouintzis, V. (2010). The experience of bullying among secondary school students. *Psychology in The Schools*, 47(4), 328-341, Doi:10.1080/01425690802514391.
- Bansel, P., Davies, B., Laws, C., Linnell, S. (2009). Bullies, bullying and power in the contexts of schooling. *British Journal Sociology of Education*, 30, 59–69.
- Olweus D. (1994). Bullying at school: Basic facts and effects of a school based intervention program. *Journal of Child Psychology and Psychiatry*, 35(7), 1171-1190, 10.1111/j.1469-7610.1994.tb01229.x.
- Husain, S., & Jan, A. (2015). Bullying in Elementary Schools: Its Causes and Effects on Students. *Journal of Education and Practice*, 6(19), 43-56, DOI:10.5539/ies.v10n6p44.
- Hong, J. S., Espelage, D. L. (2012). A review of research on bullying and peer victimization in school: An ecological system analysis. *Aggressive Behavior*, 17, 311–322, doi.org/10.1016/j.avb.2012.03.003.
- Jaradat, A. K. (2017). Gender differences in bullying and victimization among early adolescents in Jordan. *International Journal of Social Sciences*, doi:10.20319/pijss.2017.33.440451.
- Tera Sahjo, T., & Salmivalli, C. (2003). She is not actually bullied. The discourse of harassment in student groups. *Aggressive Behavior*, 29, 134–154, doi.org/10.1002/ab.10045.
- Silva, M. A. I., Pereira, B., Mendonça, D., Nunes, B., Abadio de Olivera, W. (2013). The involvement of girls and boys with bullying: an analysis of

gender differences. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*. Available from: www.mdpi.com/journal/ijerph doi: 10.3390/ijerph10126820.

10. Seals, D., & Young, J. (2003). Bullying and victimization: Prevalence and relationship to gender, grade level, ethnicity, self-esteem, and depression. *Adolescence*, 38, 735-747.

11. Shute, R., Owens, L., & Slee, P. (2008). Everyday victimization of adolescent girls by boys: Sexual harassment, bullying, or aggression? *Sex Roles*, 58, 477-489.

12. Navarro, R., Larrañaga, E., Yubero, S. (2011). Bullying-victimization problems and aggressive tendencies in Spanish secondary school students: The role of gender stereotypical traits. *Social Psychology Education*, 14, 457-473, doi:10.1007/s11218-011-9163-1.

13. O'Connell, P., Pepler, D. & Craig, W. (1999). Peer involvement in bullying: Insights and challenges for intervention. *Journal of Adolescence*, 22(4), 437-452, <https://doi.org/10.1006/jado.1999.0238s>.